

Shaping international standards for advanced technologies

The INSTAR European Task Forces (ETFs) are groups of European standardisation and domain experts that are actively contributing to innovate the **AI, Cybersecurity, Digital ID, IoT, 5G, 6G, Quantum Technologies, and Data Technologies** domains.

These ETFs aim to cultivate a European common vision, aligning project activities and monitoring the implementation of standards on a macro level.

Learn More

Objective 1

Support the DPs/TTC

Support future EU Digital Partnerships (DPs) and EU-US TTC meetings by organising events to collect inputs and providing summary reports with the collected insights.

Objective 2

Multilateral Engagement

Multilateral coordination with international entities on long-term common standardisation goals per each technology area.

Objective 3

Roadmap

Create a standardisation priorities roadmap to guide the activities of the SDOs, EU Digital Partnerships and EU-US TTC.

The European Task Forces

5G+/6G

AI

Cybersecurity/
eID

Data
Technologies

IoT/Edge/Cloud
& Internet

Quantum
Technologies

Our consortium

Coordinator

fortiss

